

5 December 2024

Press release

On 29 October 2024, the CST4ALL project hosted the online “Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with heat pumps”. This workshop aimed to explore the industrial potential of integrating CST and heat pump technologies. Organised by ESTELA with contributions from all CST4ALL partners and the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating & Cooling (RHC-ETIP), the event attracted over 170 stakeholders from the energy sector across 27 countries worldwide.

The workshop brought together a diverse audience, including representatives from the European Commission (EC), national authorities, industry, associations, engineering and consultancy firms, research institutions and universities.

Dr. Konstantinos Genikomsakis of ESTELA opened the event, introducing the CST4ALL project and outlining the workshop’s objectives and agenda. Dr. Yelda Erden Topal of the Middle East Technical University (METU) presented the on-going public opinion survey on Green Deal challenges & social sciences and humanities and gender aspects within the project, encouraging attendees to participate.

Philippe Schild delivered a message from the EC acknowledging the role of the CST4ALL project and its alignment with the objectives of the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan).

Keynote speakers Yuvaraj Sathiyadev Pandian (from Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH), Dr. Miguel Ramirez (from Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research, TNO) and Dr. Pankaj Kumar (from United Nations Industrial Development Organization, UNIDO) presented integration opportunities of CST and heat pumps for building heating, district heating and industrial process heat, including the example of a pharmaceutical facility in India using a CST-heat pump hybrid system for industrial process heat supply.

During a live poll, participants identified the shared use of thermal energy storage to balance energy supply and demand as the most promising synergy between CST and heat pump technologies.

The workshop’s roundtable discussion, moderated by Dr. Maurizio Pieve of ENEA, featured a panel of experts who exchanged views on technology readiness, project financing and available financial instruments, regional considerations and regulatory frameworks, skills gap, R&I priorities, as well as market dynamics and potential collaboration opportunities between the CST and heat pump sectors, including demonstration hybrid plants.

Dr. Peter Heller, coordinator of the CST4ALL project, summarised the key findings from each session. The event underscored the potential of combining CST with heat pumps to enhance renewable energy

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efficiency, particularly in industrial and district heating applications. Scaling up demonstration projects and driving innovation in thermal storage and heat pump technologies were highlighted as essential steps to address operational, financial, and technical challenges. These advancements will unlock the economic and environmental benefits of CST-heat pump hybrid systems and will accelerate the adoption of these solutions to decarbonise various industrial sectors.

This CST4ALL project event was organised with the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating & Cooling (RHC-ETIP).

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow the project on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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